

HMGCR enzyme deficiency model in mice

Version 0

Description

HMGCR enzyme deficiency model in mice is used in the mitoHMGCR project to study the physiological role of HMGCR enzyme and molecular mechanisms of statin-induced side effects. The specific objectives of the mitoHMGCR project cover delineation of detrimental effects of HMGCR deficiency in the tissue-specific KO mice models (liver and brain astrocyte), identification of biochemical markers, and therapeutic target pathways to treat HMGCR deficiency-induced sequels such as hepatotoxicity, myopathy, and neurological deficits, creation of new models and tools for testing HMGCR-targeted strategies. Collected data include metabolic phenotyping and mitochondrial functionality measures. Energy metabolite levels were analyzed in tissue and blood samples from a mice model of HMGCR enzyme KO. Transcriptomics data provide information regarding the involved signalling pathways.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research Projects (Izp-2023/1-
0287)

Researchers

Maija Dambrova

Organizations

Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [HMGCR enzyme deficiency model in mice](#)

Description:

HMGCR enzyme deficiency model in mice is used in the mitoHMGCR project to study the physiological role of HMGCR enzyme and molecular mechanisms of statin-induced side effects. The specific objectives of the mitoHMGCR project cover delineation of detrimental effects of HMGCR deficiency in the tissue-specific KO mice models (liver and brain astrocyte), identification of biochemical markers, and therapeutic target pathways to treat HMGCR deficiency-induced sequels such as hepatotoxicity, myopathy, and neurological deficits, creation of new models and tools for testing HMGCR-targeted strategies. Collected data include metabolic phenotyping and mitochondrial functionality measures. Energy metabolite levels were analyzed in tissue and blood samples from a mice model of HMGCR enzyme KO. Transcriptomics data provide information regarding the involved signalling pathways.

Researchers:

[Maija Dambrova](#)

Organizations:

[Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis](#)

Contact: [Maija Dambrova \(maija.dambrova@farm.osi.lv\)](mailto:maija.dambrova@farm.osi.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Fundamental and Applied Research Projects \(lzp-2023/1-0287\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-05-20](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Metadata of the study: HMGCR activity is essential for mitochondrial β -oxidation of fatty acids to prevent lethal accumulation of long-chain acylcarnitines in the mouse liver

Metadata of the study "HMGCR activity is essential for mitochondrial β -oxidation of fatty acids to prevent lethal accumulation of long-chain acylcarnitines in the mouse liver" published in Br J Pharmacol 2024. Apr 19. doi: 10.1111/bph.16363.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The specific objectives of the mitoHMGCR project cover delineation of detrimental effects of HMGCR deficiency in the tissue-specific KO mice models (liver and brain astrocyte), identification of biochemical markers, and therapeutic target pathways to treat HMGCR deficiency-induced sequels such as hepatotoxicity, myopathy, and neurological deficits, creation of new models and tools for testing HMGCR-targeted strategies.

Collected data include metabolic phenotyping and mitochondrial functionality measures. Energy metabolite levels were analyzed in tissue and blood samples from preclinical experiments. Transcriptomics data provide information regarding the involved signalling pathways.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We consider re-using existing data in new drug target discovery and safety assessment projects.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful for researchers interested in mitochondrial and peroxisomal metabolism of lipids and side effects of statin drugs.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata reported in publication: Liepinsh E, Zvejniece L, Clemensson L, Ozola M, Vavers E, Cirule H, Korzh S, Skuja S, Groma V, Briviba M, Grinberga S, Liu W, Olszewski P, Gentreau M, Fredriksson R, Dambrova M, Schiöth HB.

Hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA reductase activity is essential for mitochondrial β -oxidation of fatty acids to prevent lethal accumulation of long-chain acylcarnitines in the mouse liver. Br J Pharmacol. 2024 Apr 19. doi: 10.1111/bph.16363.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/11203607>

LIOS community

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

For most data, no special software is needed and standard programs (Windows Office) are sufficient to access and (re-)analyze the data.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

For most data, no special software is needed and standard programs (Windows Office) are sufficient to access and (re-)analyze the data.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-05-22

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project's budget.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Maija Dambrova

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Institutional funding

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Ethical approval of study protocol involving KO animals.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

